

Glossary for the Flemish DMP template

Accession number: A unique identifier assigned to a dataset, record, or other digital object when it is submitted to a data repository. Accession numbers are typically used by domain-specific repositories (e.g., Gene Expression Omnibus, European Nucleotide Archive) to enable persistent access, tracking, and citation of deposited materials. Unlike DOIs, which are standardised and globally resolvable, accession numbers are repository-specific.

Closed access: In general, closed access refers to resources or content that is locked behind some type of barrier, such as a paywall or an access request. In the context of Table 5.1 of the DMP template, however, we use closed access more specifically to mean datasets that you intend not to publish in a public data repository at all and will therefore remain unfindable to the public. Keep in mind that institutional storage drives do not count as public access.

Commercial valorisation: The process of creating value from knowledge by making knowledge suitable or available for economic use and translating that knowledge into marketable products, services, or technologies.¹ This may involve patenting, licensing, creating spin-off companies, and/or partnering with industry. Researchers with potential for commercial valorisation are encouraged to consult their institution's legal department (e.g., Tech Transfer Office) for guidance.

Data format: The way in which the data is encoded for storage, often reflected by the filename extension (for example pdf, xlsx, docx, txt, or rdf).²

Data types:

- **Audiovisual:** A series of visual representations imparting an impression of motion when shown in succession. May or may not include sound.
- **Numerical:** Quantitative data that represents measurable quantities.
- **Image:** A non-moving visual representation other than text.
- **Model:** An abstract, conceptual, graphical, mathematical or visualization model that represents empirical objects, phenomena, or physical processes.
- **Software:** A computer program in source code (text) or compiled form. Use this type for all software components supporting scholarly research.
- **Text:** A resource consisting primarily of words for reading. Examples are transcripts, reports, administrative documents, or academic articles by others that you use as a resource for research.
- **Workflow:** A structured series of steps which can be executed to produce an outcome, allowing users a means to specify and enact their work in a more reproducible manner.
- **Physical object:** An inanimate, three-dimensional object or substance.

¹ Based on van Drooge, L. & de Jong, S. (2023). Valorisation: researchers already do much more than they realise. <https://www.rathenau.nl/en/knowledge-and-innovation-transitions/definitions-and-policy>

² Science Europe. (2021). Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management - Extended Edition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4915862> (p.18)

Data usage license: A data usage license specifies whether and how data can be reused, including any conditions or restrictions. Unless you have a license, data may be ‘publicly available’, but users will not have permission to access, use and share it under copyright or database laws.³ Note that you may only assign a license of your choice to data if they are not already subject to an existing license that restricts such use. The Creative Commons (CC) standard licenses are a widely used set of licenses that allow data creators to clearly communicate how others may use their work. See [Creative Commons](#) for definitions on the different types of CC licenses. If you want to share software (source code), you can choose from a wide variety of open-source software licenses. You can use license selectors, such as [this one](#), to help you find the license most appropriate to you.

Dataset: Organised collection of data or objects that are generated or collected by researchers during their investigations, regardless of their form or method, that form the object on which researchers test a hypothesis. This includes the full range of data: raw, unprocessed datasets, proprietary generated and processed data, and secondary data obtained from third parties.⁴

Documentation: Information needed to understand and enable the re-use of data. This may include information on the methodology used to collect the data, analytical and procedural information, definitions of variables, units of measurement, and so on. This information can be captured in different ways, for example in a database with links to each item, a README file, file headers, codebooks, or lab notebooks. Documentation can thus range from a simple README file describing the data to highly structured metadata generated by specific measurement instruments.

DOI: Digital Object Identifier. A name (not a location) for an entity on digital networks. It provides a system for persistent and actionable identification and interoperable exchange of managed information on digital networks. A DOI is a type of Persistent Identifier (PID) issued by the International DOI Foundation. This permanent identifier is associated with a digital object that permits it to be referenced reliably even if its location and metadata undergo change over time.

Dual use: Dual-use items are goods, software and technology which can be used for both civil and military purposes. This does not mean that you as a researcher are aiming for a military application of your research, but rather that your research or the materials you use may lend themselves to this.⁵

Embargoed access: Refers to a resource that is metadata only access until released for open access on a certain date. Embargoes can be required by publishers and funders policies or set by the author.

Encryption: a data protection technique that transforms readable data (plaintext) into an unreadable format (ciphertext) using algorithms and encryption keys. Encryption safeguards research data during storage and transmission, ensuring that only authorized individuals with the correct decryption key can access the original information.

Ethical considerations: When conducting research, especially involving humans, animals and/or when there is a potential for dual use, specialised and more experienced feedback on ethical considerations may be necessary. Ethical considerations ensure that research is conducted responsibly, with respect

³ See <https://data.europa.eu/elearning/en/module4/#/id/co-01>

⁴ Based on CODATA RDM Terminology Working Group. (2024). CODATA RDM Terminology (2023, v0001): overview (2023, v0001). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10626170>

⁵ For more details, see: VLIR. (2022). Guidelines for researchers on dual use and misuse of research. <https://vlir.be/publicaties/richtlijnen-dual-use/>

for human rights, scientific integrity, and societal benefit. The party responsible for providing such feedback is usually an Ethics Committee (EC) at your institution or faculty.⁶ These committees are specifically established to support researchers in evaluating ethical considerations relevant to their work. If your institution does not have a specialised body for reviewing ethical consideration, then you as a researcher are still expected to conduct your research with the utmost attention to ethical standards. You can guide your scientific research by checking ethical guidelines in your specific field or by following a general ethical guidelines such as the [Code of Ethics For Scientific Research In Belgium](#).

Intellectual property rights: The most common intellectual property rights are those protecting a (technical) invention, a trademark, a new plant variety, (industrial) designs and literary/artistic works. If you are collaborating with external partners, it is important to clarify who owns the IPR of the creations resulting from the research.

Metadata: Metadata is data about data. It is data (or information) that defines and describes the characteristics of other data. It is used to improve the understanding and use of the data. Metadata play a key role in making your data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR). Metadata have to be added continuously to your research data, not just at the beginning or at the end of a project. Metadata can be added manually or automatically, and preferably according to a disciplinary standard. The distinction between data and metadata is not ontological, but it is grounded in use. What is “data” and what is “metadata” is thereby a matter of perspective: Some researchers’ metadata can be other researchers’ data. While data documentation is meant to be read and understood by humans, metadata are primarily meant to be processed by machines.⁷

Metadata only (access level): Refers to a resource in which access is limited to metadata only. The resource itself is described by the metadata, but neither is directly available through the system or platform nor can be referenced to an open access copy in an external journal or trustworthy archive.

Open access: The practice of providing online access to research outputs, free of charge to the end-user, and without any legal or technical barriers, such as the requirement to have a user account or to solve a captcha.

Persistent identifier: A persistent identifier is a long-lasting reference to a digital object that gives information about that object regardless of what happens to it. Developed to address “link rot,” a persistent identifier can be resolved to provide an appropriate representation of an object whether that object changes its online location or goes offline.

Personal data: Personal data is any information that relates to an identified or identifiable living individual. Different pieces of information, which collected together can lead to the identification of a particular person, also constitute personal data. Personal data that has been de-identified, encrypted or pseudonymised but can be used to re-identify a person remains personal data and falls within the scope of the GDPR. Personal data that has been rendered anonymous in such a way that the individual is not or no longer identifiable is no longer considered personal data. For data to be truly anonymised, the anonymisation must be irreversible. Examples of personal data:

⁶ Points of contacts are listed on the FWO website: <https://www.fwo.be/en/about-fwo/research-policy/research-ethics/>

⁷ <https://www.howtofair.dk/how-to-fair/metadata/>

- A name and surname;
- A home address;
- An email address such as name.surname@company.com;
- An identification card number;
- Location data (for example the location data function on a mobile phone);
- An Internet Protocol (IP) address;
- A cookie ID;
- The advertising identifier of your phone;
- Data held by a hospital or doctor, which could be a symbol that uniquely identifies a person.

Physical, non-digital, or analogue data or research materials: Physical data are equally considered research data. Obviously, these data require a completely different approach regarding, for example, storage and preservation. Examples: paper-based questionnaires and notes, archaeological findings, art works (e.g., paintings, sculptures, photographs), protein and blood samples, nucleic acids, building plans, recordings on tapes or discs.

Privacy register (also referred to as **GDPR register, data register, processing register**): An institutional record of the processing of personal data within research projects. To ensure transparency, accountability, and compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), it is mandatory to document all processing activities involving personal data by completing the institution's privacy register. Each entry must include critical elements such as the types of personal data processed, the individuals or roles responsible for processing, and the purpose of processing. Maintaining an up-to-date privacy register is essential for facilitating internal audits, responding to data subject requests, and demonstrating GDPR compliance to supervisory authorities (e.g., the Data Protection Authority or GBA).

Pseudonymisation: the processing of personal data in such a manner that the personal data can no longer be attributed to a specific data subject without the use of additional information, provided that such additional information is kept separately and is subject to technical and organisational measures (e.g., encryption, access control) to ensure that the personal data are not attributed to an identified or identifiable natural person.

Repository: A digital platform where research data are stored, managed, and made accessible for long-term preservation and sharing. In RDM, repositories may be institutional, disciplinary, or general-purpose, and typically provide metadata, persistent identifiers, and access controls to ensure data can be discovered, cited, and reused in accordance with legal, ethical, and funder requirements. An example of a registry of data repositories is re3data.org where you can find an overview of repositories with various features (e.g., certification, restricted access, licenses, use of metadata standards...).

Research data: Research data are any information collected or generated for the purpose of analysis, in order to generate or validate scientific claims. It includes digital and physical data. Research data encompass the whole spectrum ranging from raw data to the processed and analysed data. Examples include survey results, statistics, measurements, notebooks, images, texts, computer generated data, simulations, software developed for research purposes, computational metadata, prints, video- and audiotapes, coding of textual information, organisms, gene sequences, synthetic compounds, samples, patients data, etc.

Restricted access: Refers to a resource that is available in a system but with some type of restriction for full open access. This type of access can occur in a number of different situations. For example:

- The user must log in to the system in order to access the resource;
- The user must send an email to the author or system administrator to access the resource;
- Access to the resource is restricted to a specific community (e.g., limited to a university community);
- Access to the resource requires signing a data use agreement (or any other agreement).

Volumes: Volumes can be expressed in storage space required (bytes), and/or in numbers of objects, files, rows, and columns.